

HARMONISED PRACTICES, REGULATIONS AND STANDARDS
IN WASTE MANAGEMENT AND DECOMMISSIONING

Deliverable D2.2

**Analysis of stakeholder
engagement results and
definition of priority areas**

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ABSTRACT

The 3-year HARPERS project aims to establish and clarify the benefits and added value of more aligned and harmonised practices, methodologies and approaches in decommissioning and the initial phase of radioactive waste handling, as well as for shared processing, storage and disposal facilities between Member States. The project will also identify the obstacles and issues that could hamper the implementation of a more aligned approach with recommendations to overcome them.

The focus is on three categories of activities: *cross border services and facilities, moving to a circular economy and implementation of advanced technologies.*

In a first phase of the project we focus on engaging with stakeholders to assess needs and pros/cons for harmonisation and identify priority areas for deeper analysis in phase 2 of the project. Stakeholder engagement sessions were organised for the three “technical” workpackages: WP3 – Cross border services and facilities, WP4 – Circular economy and WP5 Advanced technologies.

The aim of the engagement sessions was to discuss identified priority areas/topics that resulted from a broad “gap analysis” exercise, targeting aspects of harmonisation of practices, methodologies and approaches in the fields of decommissioning and radioactive waste management and to ensure the highest prioritisation in project focus and greatest impact of the project outcomes in Phase 2 of the project.

This report summarises the outcome of the stakeholder engagement sessions and the outcome of the final prioritisation process to arrive to a shortlist of priority topics (9 topics).

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1 Version history

Version	Date	Author	Comments
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1. Introduction

The 3-year HARPERS project aims to establish and clarify the benefits and added value of more aligned and harmonised practices, methodologies and approaches in decommissioning and the initial phase of radioactive waste handling, as well as for shared processing, storage and disposal facilities between Member States. The project will also identify the obstacles and issues that could hamper the implementation of a more aligned approach with recommendations to overcome them.

The focus is on three categories of activities: cross border services and facilities, moving to a circular economy and implementation of advanced technologies.

In a first phase of the project we focus on engaging with stakeholders to assess needs and pros/cons for harmonisation and identify priority areas for deeper analysis in Phase II of the project.

The aim of the engagement sessions with stakeholders was to discuss identified priority areas/topics, that resulted from a broad “gap analysis” exercise, targeting aspects of harmonisation of practices, methodologies and approaches in the fields of decommissioning and waste management. In addition, they would ensure the highest prioritisation in project focus and greatest impact of the project outcomes in Phase 2 of the project.

For each of the three “technical” work packages:

- WP3 – Cross border services and facilities,
- WP4 – Circular economy
- WP5 – Advanced technologies

the outcome of the stakeholder engagement sessions and the outcome of the final prioritisation process to arrive to a shortlist of priority topics (9 topics) is summarised in this report. An overview of the process is shown in Figure 1 below.

This report complements “D2.1 work methodologies: methods for identification and prioritisation of topics” (<https://www.harpers-h2020.eu/documents.html>).

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Figure 1: Timeline presenting the different steps during Phase 1 of the HARPERS project.

Based on the outcome of this entire process, open calls will be organised allowing small teams of partners (~3-4 organisations), both consortium and external partners, to apply for further development of the final selected priority topics. The 9 topics will be presented in the open calls with necessary background and suggested areas for development for the potential parties to submit proposals to undertake in the next phase. These open calls will be launched by July 2023 and after selection of the teams/topics, the actual work of the “refinement phase (Phase 2)” can start (November 2023). In this refinement phase the teams will investigate more in detail the issues associated with the selected topic. This also entails a deeper engagement with Stakeholders relevant to the specific topic.

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2 Stakeholder engagement

The ultimate aim of Phase 1 of the HARPERS project is to produce a reduced list of topics (~9, to be distributed evenly among the technical Work packages) that are considered of priority interest for further development in the 2nd phase of the project through open calls to which small teams of experts, consortium and external partners, can subscribe. These teams will further engage with the Stakeholder community.

As documented in D2.1 (<https://www.harpers-h2020.eu/documents.html>), the Stakeholder community was identified and all willing participants were prepared for engagement. An in-depth gap analysis was performed to define priority needs and opportunities (thematic questions) and criteria were identified that can help in setting up priority topics/projects based on drivers related to implementation. These inputs were combined in an engagement process with the Stakeholder community where the list of identified topics was discussed in order to take their inputs into a further fine-tuning and down-selection of priority topics. This to ensure the highest prioritisation in project focus, relevance to the key stakeholders and greatest impact of the project outcomes.

Each “technical” work package (WP3, WP4, WP5), organised two online workshops spread over a period of 2-3 months in the first quarter of 2023 providing possibilities for project partners (internal Stakeholders) and external (registered) Stakeholders to take part in one or both of the sessions in the engagement process. In the engagement process, *Slido* was used as an online tool for polling/voting to capture the inputs of the stakeholder on a list of pre-defined open questions and to gather data on the needs/challenges that the technical work packages had identified.

Dates of the Stakeholder engagement workshops (2023):

- WP3: 19/01 & 08/03
- WP4: 16/01 & 22/02
- WP5: 18/01 & 02/02
- General session: 30/05 - feedback to the stakeholders on the outcome of the sessions (consolidation of the results, <https://www.harpers-h2020.eu/documents.html>).

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Each Stakeholder session was planned to take 2 hrs and followed a common agenda:

- Workshop opening by WP leader
- General introduction of HARPERS project by project coordinator
- Participants self-introduction
- Part 1 WP introduction + slido Polls (WP lead)
- Q&A – open discussion (WP lead + supports)
- Break
- Part 2 identified needs & opportunities (topics) introduction + Slido Polls (WP lead)
- Q&A – open discussion (WP lead + supports)
- Closure of the Workshop (WP lead)

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3 Selection of topics to launch through open calls

In view of the input, thoughts, and visions expressed by the Stakeholders and the list of defined selection criteria, a final selection of 3 priority topics per WP was made within the WP through the use of a defined selection criteria and methodology. Key considerations for this final selection are:

- Transparent selection approach
- Take into account the input of the Stakeholder engagement process (Slido Polls, remarks, covering both quantitative and qualitative data)
- Use the selection criteria defined before (“drivers”).

Where needed a semi-quantitative approach is applied to rank the priority topics. Based on the Slido polls weighting factors can be applied to categories, drivers, challenges & needs, impact of topics on main drivers (depending on the WP). This “quantitative” ranking was further discussed within the WP with consortium partners and if needed a further down selection was made using qualitative analysis tools like importance/urgency, impact/effort matrices (not limited).

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4 WP3 Cross border services and facilities for radioactive waste management - Workshop outcome and prioritised topics

HARPERS Work Package 3 aims to identify the most important conditions and opportunities for establishing activities related to cross border services and facilities for radioactive waste management. As a part of Phase 1a of the project a detailed list of topics proposed for deep analysis in Phase 2 has been developed within WP3 (see D2.1, <https://www.harpers-h2020.eu/documents.html>, and annex 8.1), based on the input of the different partners and on the review conducted on the existing literatures. The topics were clustered into 4 main categories reflecting the “challenge/need” and the “why”:

- Harmonisation
- Best practices
- Technical challenges
- Geological disposal facilities and waste storage facilities.

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4.1 Summary of SH engagement outcome

The stakeholders were requested to “vote” for the different topics in the different categories and to provide answers (through slido + email) to 3 open questions.

Q1 - What are the main benefits of cross border services/facilities for radioactive waste?

Radioactive Waste?

Wordcloud Poll 36 responses 22 participants

	SLIDO	EMAIL
Economical	7	3
Efficiency (share)	11	7
Ability to treat waste for all MS., sustainability	3	6

Three areas stand out:

- Efficiency (share)
- Economical
- Ability to treat waste for all Member States, sustainability.

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Q2 - What is the single most important need for you?

a new one. One or two short statements please.

Wordcloud Poll 16 responses 16 participants

	SLIDO	EMAIL
Experience exc.	3	3
Waste routes and minimization	6	3
Availability	4	4

Three areas stand out:

- Waste routes and minimization
- Availability
- Experience exchange

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Q3 - What is the single most difficult barrier stopping cross border services, as you see it?

you see it? One short statement please.

Wordcloud Poll 21 responses 17 participants

	SLIDO	EMAIL
Regulatory	10	3
Public	5	4

Two areas stand out:

- Regulatory aspects (lack of harmonisation)
 - Are all regulators in EU using the same foundation? Yes! EU directives
 - Question is therefore: Who is actually creating the approach of how to deal with different “issues”? Regulators? Companies? Politicians? Others? Combination?
- Public acceptance, opinion, etc.
 - Include in the selection

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Conclusions

- Each workshop involved around 20-30 participants (>7 External Stakeholders)
- Having an efficient and economic cross border service/facility were indicated as the main drivers for radioactive waste management.
- Experience, availability and a defined waste route were identified as the top “needs” when it comes to cross border services and facilities.
- An overall conclusion is that there is a strong requirement for a harmonised approach in the areas of regulation which is needed to improve radioactive waste treatment.

4.2 Prioritisation of the topics

From the outcome of the workshop (topic voting) the category on geological disposal related topics was removed from further prioritization. And weighting factors were applied based on the votings, importance of the challenge (regulatory, economical, societal) and impact.

A more detailed description of the prioritization process can be found in D3.1 (<https://www.harpers-h2020.eu/documents.html>).

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The prioritisation process leads to following 3 topics:

Topic	What (challenge/need)	Why
1	To align wastes with treatment technologies in a manner acceptable to all stakeholders	A common understanding of the suitability of treatment options for different waste type is required to establish new shared waste processing opportunities. Noting that stakeholders may have differing views on the suitability of treatment options for certain wastes.
2	Harmonisation of Individual EU and international countries problematic waste inventory	Provides EU with data to produce a strategy to efficiently treat problematic wastes before long term storage. This should focus on problematic or challenging wastes that do not have a treatment solution already
3	Member States approach to dealing with radioactive contaminated hazardous waste differs	Emerging radioactive contaminated hazardous waste streams may require cross border technical solutions

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5 WP4 Circular economy - Workshop outcome and prioritised topics

HARPERS Workpackage 4 aims to identify the most important conditions and opportunities for establishing a Circular Economy in radioactive waste management activities across Europe. As a part of Phase 1a of the project a detailed list of topics proposed for deep analysis in Phase 2 has been developed within WP4 (see D2.1, <https://www.harpers-h2020.eu/documents.html>, and annex 8.2), based on the input of the different partners and on the review conducted on the existing literatures. The topics were clustered into 7 main categories (inventory, recycling and reuse, technologies for material and waste treatment, clearance, characterization, multi criteria analysis of strategies and transversal aspects) as reported Deliverable 2.1.

5.1 Summary of SH engagement outcome

The first part of the workshop was aimed at introducing Circular Economy in radioactive waste management and posing a set of polls to the stakeholders by using Slido tool in order to obtain their feedback on questions related to the topic in discussion. The second part of the Workshop was devoted to a description of the Topics identified in the gap analysis (WP2) for the theme circular economy. Topics were grouped in 7 categories as mentioned above e.g. inventory, recycling and reuse, technologies for material and waste treatment, clearance, characterization, multi criteria analysis of strategies and transversal aspects.

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Q1 - Why circular economy is important for nuclear decommissioning and radioactive waste management

Q2 – What are the main drivers for implementing circular economy in radioactive waste management?

Q3+Q6 – What are the most important themes to be further analysed within HARPERS project for promoting circular economy when managing materials and waste coming from nuclear decommissioning?

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Q4 – What are the main challenges (barriers) for reuse and recycling?

Q5 – What are the main challenges (needs) associated with clearance of waste and materials arising from decommissioning?

Open discussion

1st session

Before topics description

- Transversal category: societal issues should be separated from the KM and good practices
- Attention focused on the cross interaction between the different categories and topics to be considered in the analysis (e.g. inventory management and characterization are linked with recycling strategies)

2nd session

- Need to clearly communicate the relevance of circular economy (not only financial aspects)
- knowledge sharing and stakeholder engagement linked to the driver: build trust and competence

After topics description

- Societal aspects seems to be a dominant theme especially for reuse and recycling
- Economic benefit (but also societal ones) in recycling and reuse as a fundamental aspect to be considered
- Change of mind is needed and sharing good practices for recycling
- Parallel projects ongoing on regulatory aspects (e.g. technical exchanges on conditional clearance within IAEA) and HARPERS can benefit from the outcomes of such exchanges.
- Valuable materials cannot be recycled nowadays because of regulatory constraints.
- Sharing of current/good practices could help in building trust in the recycling of materials

Conclusions

- Each workshop involved around 35-36 participants (4-7 External Stakeholders)
- Sustainability and waste minimization were indicated as the main reasons why Circular Economy is important for nuclear decommissioning and radioactive waste management.
- Protection of citizens and environment, economic renewal and growth and public trust and confidence as the top 3 drivers for implementing Circular Economy in radioactive waste management
- Recycling and Reuse and Clearance as the most important topics. No strong expectations were highlighted with regards to Inventory or Characterisation.

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- Regulatory discrepancies and regulatory constraints as the main challenge for clearance and material recycling. Societal aspects were indicated as a dominant theme and sharing of current/good practices could help in building trust in the recycling of materials

5.2 Prioritisation of the topics

The prioritisation was done in a semi-quantitative approach based on:

- Identification and assignment of **Weighting factors** to:
 - Categories
 - Drivers
 - Challenges
- Analysis of the **impact of the topics on the top drivers**
- Qualitative evaluation of the top priority topics in terms of **Importance, Urgency and Achievability**

For more details on the prioritization process we refer to D4.1 (<https://www.harpers-h2020.eu/documents.html>).

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The prioritisation process leads to following 3 topics.

Topic	Description of topic	Main challenges	Main needs
1	Identification of regulatory discrepancies for free release, unconditional and conditional clearance. Analysis of criteria and guidance for clearance and for reuse and recycling	Different national regulations	Promote harmonised criteria and regulations (policies) to enable reuse and recycling, preserve natural resources and minimising the waste to be disposed of
2	Benchmarking of approaches implemented in nuclear fields for reuse of structure, systems and components (including reuse of the site) Benchmarking of available technologies and circular economy approaches already implemented in non-nuclear field	Different approaches/regulations (eg. for non-nuclear into nuclear)	Sharing of best practices and gain information and lessons learned for a more sustainable decommissioning and for minimising waste and recovering and reusing valuable materials
3	Socio-economical assessment of the different strategies envisaged (linear vs circular) including analysis of costs and time needed for implementation of recycling solutions and identification of societal constraints and ways to overcome these constraints	Societal and Economical	Assess the economical, environmental/societal benefits and facilitate decision making Promote use and create market for recycled materials

6 WP5 Advanced Technologies - Workshop outcome and prioritised topics

HARPERS Workpackage 5 aims to identify the most important conditions and opportunities for establishing “Advanced Technologies” in radioactive waste management activities across Europe. As a part of Phase 1a of the project a detailed list of topics proposed for deep analysis in Phase 2 has been developed within WP5 (see D2.1, <https://www.harpers-h2020.eu/documents.html>, and annex 8.3), based on the input of the different partners and on the review conducted on the existing literatures. The topics were clustered into 3 categories: Waste treatment, Automation and Robotics, Digitalisation as reported Deliverable 2.1.

6.1 Summary of SH engagement outcome

In the workshops, the first questions were open to obtain the stakeholders views on major opportunities for advanced technologies and the main drivers. The following questions were targeted towards the topics within the defined 3 main categories.

General Q1 – What do you see as the major opportunities for advanced technologies in decommissioning and waste management in the next 10/15 years

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Increased **efficiency** was highlighted as the main opportunity/benefit for adopting advanced technologies leading to reduced costs (**cost efficiency, cost reduction**). Use of technologies, such as **robotics** and **virtual reality**, can support increased **safety and security** and provide greater **protection of people**. Adoption of advanced technologies was also seen as a benefit for **public engagement**.

General Q2 – What are the main drivers for adopting advanced technologies?

The main drivers for adopting advanced technologies, as voted by participants, were ‘Protection of citizens / environment’ and the ‘Capacity to improve performance’.

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Waste Treatment Q1 – What do you consider are the most important topics under ‘waste treatment’ to be further analysed within the HARPERS project?

Waste Treatment Q2 – What are the main challenges (barriers) associated with these topics?

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Automation & Robotics Q1 – What do you consider are the most important topics under “automation and robotics” to be further analysed within HARPERS project?

Automation & Robotics Q2 – What are the main challenges (barriers) associated with these topics?

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Digitalisation Q1 – What do you consider are the most important topics under “digitalisation” to be further analysed within the HARPERS project?

Digitalisation Q2 – What are the main challenges (barriers) associated with these topics?

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Conclusion

The most important topics (top 3 in each category) based on the views of the workshop participants are listed below.

Waste treatment

- New technologies for decontamination of buildings and environmental restoration
- New waste treatment and immobilisation technologies
- Remote in-situ characterisation / non-contact or non-destructive evaluation

The main challenges/barriers were considered to be related to Regulatory issues.

Automation and Robotics

- Adoption of robotics in decommissioning and waste management
- Automation of waste sorting, segregation, sentencing and packaging
- Smart decontamination techniques

The main challenges/barriers were indicated to be associated with Regulatory and Technological and operational issues.

Digitalisation

- Standardized digital twin and BIM technology and their application
- Standardization of protocols for security of data and data transfer
- Automation of site mapping – coupling the use of sensors, GIS and deployment methods

The main challenges/barriers were indicated to be associated with Regulatory and Technological and operational issues.

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6.2 Prioritisation of the topics

- Weighting factors for challenges

- Weighting factors for drivers and topic scores

- Evaluation of top scoring topics in each category according to Importance/Urgency and Impact/Effort Matrices

A more detailed description of the prioritization process can be found in D5.1 (<https://www.harpers-h2020.eu/documents.html>).

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The prioritisation process leads to following 3 topics

Topic	Description of topic	Main challenges	Main needs
1	New technologies for decontamination of buildings and environmental restoration including waste treatment and immobilisation	Technological and operational Regulatory	Need for standard approaches to technology assessment and qualification Need for compatibility of technologies with waste form qualification Need for guidance and sharing of experience on new decontamination products/tools and remediation technologies, particularly deployment and secondary waste aspects Need for transfer of knowledge from more advanced to less advanced programmes
2	Adoption of robotics in decommissioning planning, dismantling and waste management – new technology in nuclear environments e.g. (semi) autonomous systems, AI focused technologies, exoskeletons, wearable technology, augmented reality. To include automation of waste sorting, application of smart decontamination techniques, segregation, sentencing, packaging and storage.	Regulatory Technological and operational	Demonstration of security and safety to regulators Need for close communication with regulators during technology development Demonstrating applicability in a range of environments from basic to harsh Need for guidance on safety case demonstration appropriate to the environment Standardisation of architecture for robotics and standards for manufacturing to support verification and validation stages Need for standardisation of protocols, control systems and interfaces Need for transfer of knowledge and technologies from other industries and sharing of experience Need for sharing experience where robotics has been evaluated and used on sites for different applications

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<p>3</p>	<p>'Standardised' DTw and advanced BIM technology and their application, to include protocols for security of data and data transfer, including cyber security and segregation, digital architecture and frameworks - common human machine interface (HMI) which will also benefit modelling protocols (3D).</p>	<p>Technological and operational Regulatory</p>	<p>Need for standardised digital technologies and best practice guidance Need for guidelines/standards on the implementation of digital technologies, the data used and generated and the data quality (how to qualify this) - data protocols Need to build competency of users to assess and use the data from digital technologies - skills and interfaces Need to evaluate the regulatory implications of using advanced digital technologies Need for sharing of experience where technologies are already deployed in nuclear sector Security of data used with digital technologies, including storage, access and transfer; cyber security Need to understand what needs to be/what can be standardised involving cross-industry engagement and regulators Need for digital technologies to be accessible to users (e.g. plant owners/operators) without requiring knowledge of the underpinning coding/technology Need to agree on what needs to be/what can be standardised in terms of architecture and frameworks involving cross-industry engagement Lack of standardisation in the nuclear industry for use of 3D modelling and simulation, typically constrained by the offerings of a specific technology platform provider Need for interoperability of digital technologies for modelling and simulation</p>
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7 Consolidated list of the selected priority topics

7.1 WP3 Cross border services/facilities

Topic	What (challenge/need)	Why
1	To align wastes with treatment technologies in a manner acceptable to all stakeholders	A common understanding of the suitability of treatment options for different waste type is required to establish new shared waste processing opportunities. Noting that stakeholders may have differing views on the suitability of treatment options for certain wastes.
2	Harmonisation of Individual EU and international countries problematic waste inventory	Provides EU with data to produce a strategy to efficiently treat problematic wastes before long term storage. This should focus on problematic or challenging wastes that do not have a treatment solution already
3	Member States approach to dealing with radioactive contaminated hazardous waste differs	Emerging radioactive contaminated hazardous waste streams may require cross border technical solutions

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7.2 WP4 Circular economy

Topic	Description of topic	Main challenges	Main needs
1	Identification of regulatory discrepancies for free release, unconditional and conditional clearance. Analysis of criteria and guidance for clearance and for reuse and recycling	Different national regulations	Promote harmonised criteria and regulations (policies) to enable reuse and recycling, preserve natural resources and minimising the waste to be disposed of
2	Benchmarking of approaches implemented in nuclear fields for reuse of structure, systems and components (including reuse of the site) Benchmarking of available technologies and circular economy approaches already implemented in non-nuclear field	Different approaches/regulations (eg. for non-nuclear into nuclear)	Sharing of best practices and gain information and lessons learned for a more sustainable decommissioning and for minimising waste and recovering and reusing valuable materials
3	Socio-economical assessment of the different strategies envisaged (linear vs circular) including analysis of costs and time needed for implementation of recycling solutions and identification of societal constraints and ways to overcome these constraints	Societal and Economical	Assess the economical, environmental/societal benefits and facilitate decision making Promote use and create market for recycled materials

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7.3 WP5 Advanced Technologies

Topic	Description of topic	Main challenges	Main needs
1	New technologies for decontamination of buildings and environmental restoration including waste treatment and immobilisation	Technological and operational Regulatory	Need for standard approaches to technology assessment and qualification Need for compatibility of technologies with waste form qualification Need for guidance and sharing of experience on new decontamination products/tools and remediation technologies, particularly deployment and secondary waste aspects Need for transfer of knowledge from more advanced to less advanced programmes
2	Adoption of robotics in decommissioning planning, dismantling and waste management – new technology in nuclear environments e.g. (semi) autonomous systems, AI focused technologies, exoskeletons, wearable technology, augmented reality. To include automation of waste sorting, application of smart decontamination techniques, segregation, sentencing, packaging and storage.	Regulatory Technological and operational	Demonstration of security and safety to regulators Need for close communication with regulators during technology development Demonstrating applicability in a range of environments from basic to harsh Need for guidance on safety case demonstration appropriate to the environment Standardisation of architecture for robotics and standards for manufacturing to support verification and validation stages Need for standardisation of protocols, control systems and interfaces Need for transfer of knowledge and technologies from other industries and sharing of experience Need for sharing experience where robotics has been evaluated and used on sites for different applications
3	'Standardised' DTw and advanced BIM technology and their application, to include protocols for	Technological and operational	Need for standardised digital technologies and best practice guidance

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	<p>security of data and data transfer, including cyber security and segregation, digital architecture and frameworks - common human machine interface (HMI) which will also benefit modelling protocols (3D).</p>	<p>Regulatory</p>	<p>Need for guidelines/standards on the implementation of digital technologies, the data used and generated and the data quality (how to qualify this) - data protocols Need to build competency of users to assess and use the data from digital technologies - skills and interfaces Need to evaluate the regulatory implications of using advanced digital technologies Need for sharing of experience where technologies are already deployed in nuclear sector Security of data used with digital technologies, including storage, access and transfer; cyber security Need to understand what needs to be/what can be standardised involving cross-industry engagement and regulators Need for digital technologies to be accessible to users (e.g. plant owners/operators) without requiring knowledge of the underpinning coding/technology Need to agree on what needs to be/what can be standardised in terms of architecture and frameworks involving cross-industry engagement Lack of standardisation in the nuclear industry for use of 3D modelling and simulation, typically constrained by the offerings of a specific technology platform provider Need for interoperability of digital technologies for modelling and simulation</p>
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8 Annexes.

8.1 WP3 list of identified topics

category		Topic - What	Why
HARMONISATION	1	Harmonisation of Individual EU and international countries Problematic waste inventory	Provides EU with data to produce a strategy to efficiently treat problematic wastes before long term storage. This should focus on problematic or challenging wastes that do not have a treatment solution already.
	2	What services are wanted/what is the benefit of centralised treatment facilities.	Harmonisation of packaging or treatment across EU will lead to economic and storage benefits.
	3	Standardisation of quality control of suppliers and waste packages	If a standard QC process for waste packages is agreed across the EU, this will reduce mis consignments etc
	4	To align wastes with treatment technologies in a manner acceptable to all stakeholders	A common understanding of the suitability of treatment options for different waste types is required to establish new shared waste processing opportunities. Noting that stakeholders may have differing views on the suitability of treatment options for certain wastes
	5	A need for a common system for waste classification	Developing a common system for waste classification is a preliminary harmonization action. Could lead to implementation of potential cross-border services
BEST PRACTICE	6	Economical: Centralised vs decentralised characterisation and waste treatment review.	Harmonisation of packaging or treatment across EU will lead to economic and storage benefits.
	7	MS approach to dealing with radioactive contaminated hazardous waste differs	Emerging Radioactive contaminated hazardous waste streams may require cross border technical solutions.
	8	Share operational/regulator feedback (both good and bad) from waste treatment facilities.	Gathering data from waste management facilities will improve new facility or services lines

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category		Topic - What	Why
	9	Encouragement in cooperation to improve the safe management of radioactive wastes through building public trust and confidence in the decision-making process for hosting waste treatment facilities.	Public perception of cross border waste treatment varies between MS and the benefits to the community that cross border services facilities can bring could result in further cultural benefits to society.
	10	A need for a common approach for defining reference protocols and exp. conditions on assessment and durability and stability of conditioned waste	Standardization of test protocols for determining conditioning matrix performance could lead to increased used of specific conditioning technologies
TECHNICAL CHALLENGES	11	Methods of waste characterisation for declaration (transportation, treatment).	Declarations are sometimes unclear or not trusted, harmonisation of approaches/standards could be used to overcome this.
	12	Identify gaps & opportunities in current treatment facility needs/operations (Cross-border or mobile/modular).	Holistic review of existing facilities will demonstrate a need for additional facilities and identify possible locations based on inventory and possible provision of common treatment and conditioning schemes.
	13	Identify common EU challenging materials and waste streams.	Country by Country review of waste streams will underpin a strategy for future cross border treatment facilities.
GEOLOGICAL DISPOSAL FACILITY AND WASTE STORAGE FACILITIES	14	Standardise GDF and interim costing approach across MS.	Underpinning of GDF budgets necessary to standardise the EU GDF approach and requirements and might sign post to centralised facility needs.
	15	Sharing of intermediate waste storage facilities between MS.	Not all MS will/should have intermediate storage facilities if their inventories are small or there are additional benefits for all MS to share intermediate storage facilities.

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8.2 WP4 list of Identified topics

Category	Topic - WHAT (Challenge/Need)	WHY
INVENTORY	Common waste and radioactive materials recyclable or reusable	Surveying to find common issues for harmonised approach
	Classification and management of hazardous waste - link with European Green Deal (Circular Economy Action Plan) and the Waste Regulation	Maintain clean recycling streams and increase the confidence in using secondary raw materials
	Harmonised system to classify waste to promote circularity Inventory management as a prerequisite for circular economy	Optimising the routing of the material towards re-use and recycling will minimise the radioactive waste inventory and preserve natural resources as well as reduce the environmental impact
CLEARANCE	Free release of waste and materials arising from decommissioning (framework for clearance and regulatory discrepancies)	Minimise waste to be disposed of. Optimising the routing of the material towards re-use and recycling will minimise the radioactive waste inventory and preserve natural resources as well as reduce the environmental impact
	Framework for clearance Harmonised regulations to enable recycling Unconditional clearance: use of general limits Conditional clearance: no international guidance but only national and site-specific Clearance of very lightly contaminated liquids	Promote reuse (for free release) Promote recycling in nuclear and non-nuclear field for conditional clearance
SUSTAINABLE MATERIALS	Identification of materials that could be replaced with alternative materials	Promote and develop sustainable and bio-friendly materials
	Reduction of raw material consumption	Promote resource efficiency and more competitive and sustainable economy
	For new design reactors Recycled materials (e.g. geopolymers) for waste conditioning	
RECYCLING AND REUSE	R&D for new technologies for recovery, recycling and reusing of materials	Increase efficiency / reduce cost
	Material recycling	Improve environmental sustainability (preserve natural resources). Create a system for by-products and raw materials exchange between nuclear facilities' waste generators and potential end-users (industrial symbiosis approach).
	Create markets for recycled materials	Further promote recycling of materials and reduce costs
	Reuse of structure, systems and components (including reuse of the site)	Minimise waste and recover and reuse valuable materials
	Available technologies and circular economy approaches already implemented in non-nuclear field	Gain information and lessons learned for a more sustainable decommissioning

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Category	Topic - WHAT (Challenge/Need)	WHY
	Identification of criteria for material reusing (e.g. quality, durability, ...) - focused on material physico-chemical characteristics	Promote material reusing and reduce generation of waste
	Recycled materials traceability	Harmonised systems to track and manage information on recycled materials
	Quality assessment of recycled materials (in comparison with a new one)	Promote use and create market for recycled materials
	Public expectation / constraint, transparency and engagement around reusing and recycling	Raising public awareness on circular economy issues + societal engagement to enable recycling
	Reuse and recycle issues: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regulatory and licensing: compliance of the option with the applicable regulation (including clearance and specific criteria for recycling); Technical and operational: availability of technology and facilities to process waste; Safety and ALARA; Economic and schedule: costs, duration of implementation of solutions; Public acceptance and stakeholder Reuse of available infrastructure Enable routes for cleared wastes (e.g. metals) Benchmarking of technology for recycling and reuse	
TECHNOLOGIES FOR MATERIAL AND WASTE TREATMENT	Benchmarking of technologies and facilities for radioactive material and waste treatment	Create a widespread and structured system of technologies/facilities to be more effective
	Mobile system to reduce environmental impact and enable reuse and recycling Optimisation of treatment technologies (e.g. decontamination) to minimise waste and facilitate reuse and recycling	
MULTI CRITERIA ANALYSIS OF STRATEGIES	Digital tools and advanced technologies to support decision making processes and circular economy principles	Facilitate quick decision making and optimise decommissioning, waste management and radiation protection.
	Socio-economical assessments of the different strategies envisaged (linear vs circular)	Cost-benefit analysis to evaluate the option of reuse and recycle and facilitate decision making
	Multicriteria decision making for final end-state Cost-benefit in reuse and recycle	
CHARACTERISATION	Prerequisite for circular economy Facilities for free release Conservative clearance standards can still be a challenge	Enhance flexibility on characterisation approaches to be used for material clearance

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Category	Topic - WHAT (Challenge/Need)	WHY
	Regulatory requirements could consider different approaches: e.g., statistical approaches	
TRANSVERSAL	Societal/Public constraints/expectation Sharing good practices Regulatory engagement Knowledge Management and Training Various Stakeholder integration	

Analysis of stakeholder engagement results and definition of priority areas

8.3 WP5 list of identified topics

Category		Topic - What (Challenge/Need)	Why
WASTE TREATMENT	1	New technologies for decontamination of buildings and environmental restoration	To optimise and reduce the volume and categories of waste generated by concrete structures to be decontaminated and soils to be excavated
	2	Adoption of advanced manufacturing techniques including additive manufacturing	The use of rapid prototype /manufacturing techniques to allow for the early adoption of innovative solutions in the production of waste forms
	3	New waste treatment and immobilisation technologies	To reduce waste volumes and enhance waste-form performance. To handle difficult to treat wastes
	4	Harmonised waste-form assessment protocols	To streamline innovation in and adoption of new waste processing technologies.
	5	Remote in-situ characterisation / non-contact or non-destructive evaluation	To understand the nature of plant and waste. To reduce uncertainty in inventory, informing waste management & decommissioning strategies, decisions and appropriate automated material sentencing, including clearance of materials.
	6	Standards for mobile treatment systems	To allow cross-facility and cross-border use of treatment technologies. Supporting small inventory users. Enable cost-effective and flexible systems.
AUTOMATION AND ROBOTICS	7	'Standardised' DTw and BIM technology, to predict the performance of systems, plant, processes and packages	To enable virtual engineering to optimise decommissioning and waste management activities, through predictive modelling. To keep relevant data up to date taking into account the real progress of decommissioning works.
	8	Adoption of robotics in decommissioning planning, dismantling and waste management – new technology in nuclear environments e.g. (semi) autonomous systems, AI focused technologies, exoskeletons, wearable technology, augmented reality, are new regulatory challenges	Removing workers from hazardous exposure. Automation to reduce cost and schedule.
	9	Automation of waste sorting, segregation, sentencing and packaging.	To enhance safety and deliver efficiency gains through automation. Reduced worker exposure - ALARP.
	10	Automation of waste stores, learning from advanced digital logistics practice.	To enhance efficient waste and inventory management and safeguarding.

Analysis of stakeholder engagement results and definition of priority areas

Category		Topic - What (Challenge/Need)	Why
	11	Smart decontamination techniques - targeting contamination through sensing, local decontamination and removal of the hazard from the system.	To remove the hazard from the plant, allowing safe, but more flexible, faster, cheaper approaches to dismantling
DIGITALISATION	12	Application of advanced building information management systems to nuclear plants	To facilitate lifetime plant and waste operations, knowledge management and data retention.
	13	Standardisation of protocols for security of data and data transfer, including cyber security and segregation	To enable use of new IT solutions, and data transfer between smart devices
	14	Standardisation of digital architecture and frameworks - common human machine interface (HMI)	To allow for the cross connectivity of digital and automation tools – ‘plug and play’ and to allow and transfer between software packages. Standard HMI also aids mobility of staff between activities.
	15	Automation of site mapping – coupling the use of sensors, Geographical Information Systems (GIS) and deployment methods (UAV, land based automated vehicles etc).	Provides data for management and regulatory oversight. To facilitate efficient site mapping for radiological contamination, interpretation through modelling including Enhanced Natural Attenuation models.
	16	Standardisation of 3D modelling protocols	To allow easy transition between platforms (platform independent)